

Leveraging Technology and AI in Talent Acquisition: Analysing Their Impact on Employee Engagement and Satisfaction in Leading IT Firms in Cochin (TCS, Wipro, and CTS)

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Abstract : Integration of advanced technologies and artificial intelligence have turned recruitment into an effortless process. Modern talent acquisition which is done with the help of technology has revolutionized the impacts organizational effectiveness when compared to traditional recruitment methods. Various processes including hiring, improving candidate-job matching, and enabling data-driven decision-making helps in attracting top talents to the organisation. Impact of technology in the talent acquisition process and its effect on employee engagement and satisfaction is studied here. The study is focused on TCS, Wipro, and CTS. This research investigates how integrating Artificial Intelligence and Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) along with other technology has an impact of effectiveness of talent management. Effectiveness of various technologies in reducing hiring time, increasing recruitment accuracy and fostering employee satisfaction is also examined. A mixed-methods approach includes quantitative data collected from surveys on employee satisfaction and insights from HR professionals is taken for the study. These findings will provide insights into the use of HRIS, AI-driven analytics. The recruitment using digital platforms helps in improving HR practices in the organization. The study focuses on the role of HR strategies that are enhanced with technology in creating a competitive edge for an organizations. It focuses on the practices and space for improvement to maximize employee engagement and organizational success mainly in IT organisations.

Keywords : Artificial Intelligence, Recruitment, Talent Acquisition, Employee Engagement, Employee Satisfaction.

JEL Classification Number: M1

Introduction

Talent acquisition is an important process in IT firms because of existence of these industries in a competitive environment. This study investigate the impact of Artificial intelligence and technology in talent acquisition. By integrating HRIS, AI-based tools, and social media platforms the entire process of talent acquisition was made easy. It involves not just identifying but also attracting, and retaining the talent. IT firms are using advanced technologies to satisfy their workforce requirements, which will ensure the alignment of the individual goals of employees with organizational goals.

Talent acquisition involves

Employer Branding: Building a strong brand can be done through implementing a cohesive work culture and opportunities for growth which will help in attracting good talents.

Technology Integration: Recruitment processes in the organisation can be made effective and foolproof by using artificial intelligence, HRIS and various other technologies.

Employee Engagement: Employee satisfaction and retention is directly linked to the process of recruitment and selecting the right candidate.

Statement Of The Problem

The current industry scenario is changing rapidly. In the era of an evolving technological landscape, IT firms should focus on using AI and advanced technologies for their talent acquisition strategies compared to the traditional methods. This study is designed to determine the effectiveness of these tools in enhancing employee engagement in the organization and their satisfaction level. The challenges in adopting such technologies are also addressed in the study.

Research Objectives

- To examine how various AI-driven technologies and HRIS are used for employee hiring in Cochin-based companies such as TCS, Wipro, and CTS.
- To assess how social media platforms affect hiring effectiveness and other communications with chosen applicants.
- To comprehend the effect of technology on employee retention and satisfaction in the organization.
- To compare the modern and classic recruitment strategies that are more effective.
To investigate the challenges of using AI and other technologies to hire new employees.

Literature Review

Mohlala et al. (2024) provides an insight about human resource activities. Productivity of an organisation increases when technology is used. When systems like HRIS is used in medium and small scale industries it helps in improving decision-making skills which lead to operational effectiveness. AI integration with systems like HRIS leads to data-driven decision making. SMEs can gain a competitive edge in talent management and productivity. Issues faced by small industries in setting up technology is the implementation costs. AI solutions for smaller businesses can provide an analysis on how worker productivity can be improved. Human resource information systems (HRIS) in small and medium scale industries can help the business in scaling up.

Hunkenschroer and Kriebitz's (2023) study focuses on issues when AI-based hiring tools is used. There can be a lot of issues from a human rights angle. These perspectives can bring up the requirement of validation of the process. The study examines various factors including validity and data privacy of information which is collected by the AI system. Various moral problems can also occur during algorithmic prejudice which tend to predict or consider data of a particular type to be invalid, data exploitation can occur in an AI decision-making system. The study focuses on the use of AI and its efficiency and objectivity. AI hiring does not directly

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violate human rights. According to the survey, organizations should be ready to evaluate AI tools and safeguard privacy. The conclusion is that AI hiring is acceptable if it works with human judgment rather than as a substitute for it.

Peter and Mittal (2023) measures role of Wipro Ltd. which is a significant participant in the Indian IT sector in using AI systems in financial management of the organisation. In this study focus is given to operational effectiveness by considering the liquidity and profitability of Wipro. Examining the financial statement helps in assessing organizational effectiveness. Examining the financial results of signifies ideal liquidity and asset usage to guides to sustained growth. Research highlights the value of ratio analysis in evaluating the industry norms and future expansion prospects.

Mwaro, Ogada, and Cheruiyot (2021) studied how of neural networks is used in recruiting and selecting talents. Various Artificial Intelligence models use machine learning to develop models in hiring. This helps the organisation in focusing more towards employee retention and development. Neural network model are used to train and assess the data that are obtained from various records and reviews. During hiring process employee performance has to be also taken to consideration. Neural network model which are developed can provide a good prediction accuracy. The suggestion was that it could improve talent management and acquisition practices. The study gives information about how machine learning models are used improve talent acquisition by predictive analysis.

Fraj and Laszlo (2021) studied how artificial intelligence (AI) along with human resource management (HRM) helps in changing the hiring proces. The study examines effects of AI in hiring and selecting the right candidates by reducing human bias. The study focuses on improvement of decision-making with the help of AI through processing large amount of data. Similar way automation can be done in eliminating repetitive processes and thus enhance engagement of the applicant. Applicants like chatbots has improved hiring speed and accuracy. Sophisticated technologies can avoid problems like moral behavior from applicants. AI can promote strategic HRM practices through continuous assessment.

Allal-Chérif, Yela Aránega, and Castaño Sánchez (2021) examine the possibilities of e-recruitment with the help of digital technology. Artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized the method in which recruitment is done. Finding international talent can be done with the help of digital platform as it has the capacity to reach more candidates. Selecting and retaining these employess can be done with the capacity AI. Highlighting the hiring procedures and enhance judgment about the received applicant help the hiring process to be more effective. To improve employer branding a systematic recruitment method has to be followed in the organisation for which a proper analysis of candidates has to be done. Candidates has to be selected based on emotional intelligence and their values. The study highlights platforms including LinkedIn, MOOCs, problem-solving games, chatbots, and big data analysis.

Anupa (2021) focuses on Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) in IT organizations and their importance in improving organizational effectiveness. HR process have changed from administrative to strategic roles. Task automation and data management has helped in reducing the steps and enhancing decision-making. The study states that when technology is

implemented in long run the expenses are lower and productivity is improved. Automating HR tasks reduces the difficulty in conducting various activities in repetitive manner. Hiring and training are the major activities in an organisation which can be made more effective with technology. Payroll processing can be done with dedicated software which helps in effective managing of data and easy retrieval of information. Data privacy and employee resistance are also a significant obstacles in deploying new technology in recruitment.

Begum et al. (2020) examine how Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) reduces HR expenses and increase worker productivity in banking sector. Using HRIS in an organisation helps in improving decision-making and optimising the process efficiency. HR professionals focus on strategic goals by using HRIS to decrease errors and enable data-driven decision-making. IT-based HR systems improve business competitiveness and facilitate better resource allocation in the processes of the organisation. HR tasks like including hiring where employees are selected to the organisation, training of the selected employees and performance management.

Mujtaba and Mahapatra (2019) studied the hiring of employees using artificial intelligence. Attention is given to moral values and reducing bias. Various discussions about fairness and discrimination occurred during the research review. Focus on biases from data and human perception, which leads to judgment, will be incorporated into AI models. The dangers of employing unclean training datasets are illustrated in the study. The study looks at concepts of AI hiring processes, focusing on significant biases like selection, labeling of data, and traits in data. The study examines techniques for reducing bias while correcting data sets, changing models and patterns, and refining data, which can increase hiring efficiency by solving ethical recruitment issues.

Marrybeth et al. (2019) examines employee happiness in an organisation. Effect of talent acquisition in employee engagement is studied which contributes towards development of employees. In an organizational contexts recruitment techniques including tactics to attract larger talent pool and providing proper role clarity including job description and employee value propositions, the literature analysis finds talent acquisition and engagement as crucial factors that affect employee happiness. However, the authors point out a serious deficiency in complete human resource development (HRD) methods by pointing out that numerous institutions place little emphasis on talent development and retention. The OCTAPACE culture—which includes openness, confrontation, trust, authenticity, proactivity, autonomy, cooperation, and experimentation—is examined in the review as a mediating element in HRD activities.

Masum et al. (2018) studies Human Resource Information Systems for development of HR strategy in an organisation. Application of Management Information Systems which are knowledge based and Decision Support Systems (DSS) helps in solving HR issues. In an organisation there can be semi-structured and unstructured problems which can be easily solved with the help of an information system. Artificial intelligence (AI) when combined with these information systems provide a more efficient result. Techniques like machine learning, data mining, and neural networks are combined with information systems to develop Intelligent

Decision Support Systems (IDSS). Effective HR decision-making by considering areas like hiring, training, and talent management can be easily controlled by this approaches.

Limitations Of The Study

- Limited span due to focus only on three Cochin-based IT companies.
- Size of the sample is a limitation for statistical finding.
- Response bias can occur as self-reported data is used for the study.
- Future development and response patterns can change in according to time.
- Ethical and issues related to privacy of AI tools are not considered.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A combination of quantitative surveys with employees along with qualitative interviews with HR professionals helps in gathering information regarding the survey. This study does an analyze on the impact created by technology and AI on areas like employee engagement and satisfaction related to environment created in the organisation and how it is reflected in talent acquisition processes within leading IT firms in Cochin—TCS, Wipro, and CTS. A mixed method research where a combination of quantitative methods and qualitative methodologies are done to understand a complete overview.

Quantitative data collection using a structured questionnaire is used to do a survey among HR and Talent Acquisition professionals from TCS, Wipro, and CTS. The survey includes designed questions focused on understanding how integration of technology and AI is done in the hiring process. Qualitative data collection is done through interviews which are conducted with selected HR professionals, recruiters, and team leads in TCS, Wipro, and CTS. By combing quantitative and qualitative findings the study helps in identifying main factors, challenges, and opportunities due to the use of technology and AI in the process of talent acquisition.

Data Collection

Employees of organisation like TCS, Wipro, CTS where the respondents. Questionnaire was distributed to HR and Talent Acquisition personnel in these organisations. The purpose of the survey is to gather information on the adoption of AI powered tools and recruitment software along with social media platforms used in hiring process. For efficient and effective data collection the questionnaire was distributed through mails and other electronic communication. Through this method a diverse level of sample was achieved from the professionals working in these leading IT organisations.

To have greater involvement by the participant the survey was conducted by including detailed steps and question regarding most the activity in the organisation related to HR strategies. This mode of approach increases the openness which will help in getting good response. The

research follows to strict guidelines in ensuring confidentiality of the data collected, increase voluntary participation from the employees and consent was also obtained from all respondents.

Data Analysis

SPSS was the main statistical tool used for performing quantitative data analysis. The main focus was given on inferential analysis and descriptive statistics to analyse and identify various patterns in the dataset, relationships among variables and trends in the observed value. Systematic analysis was applied to the qualitative data received after conducting interviews and thus getting a deeper insight about the responses.

The advantage of statical tool like SPSS helps in analysis of correlations among the dataset and trends in the observed values. The observations provide a detail on how AI-powered tools and recruitment software along with social media platforms effects talent acquisition and its effectiveness in employee engagement and job satisfaction. Qualitative data is systematically identified and results are interpreted. Various benefits, challenges, and strategic advantages of using technology and AI in recruitment processes was analysed from the observed data.

Analysis And Interpretation

Mean scores of different age groups and Employee Engagement and Satisfaction.

Table 7.1

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p value</i>
EES	Below 30	54	132.14	3.23	3.484	0.009
	31–40 years	52	123.63	18.73		
	41–50 years	28	117.36	17.43		
	>50	29	118.85	27.9		

The results of ANOVA test as shown in Table 7.1 indicates that the statistical value of $p < 0.05$ which shows that there is significant difference in opinion is observed between the people of different age groups about their perception about employee engagement and satisfaction. Hence, we reject the hypothesis. The result of ANOVA indicates that for Employee Engagement and Satisfaction, 41–50 years differs with Below 30 years, > 50 years differs with Below 30 years.

Table 7.2 Multiple comparison tests

Dependent Variable		Mean Difference	Std. Error	p value
EEs	<30 years	31-40 years	8.514	0.141
		41–50 years	14.78141*	0.011

		> 50 Years	13.29540*	5.967	0.027
31–40 years		Below 30 years	-8.514	5.771	0.141
		41–50 years	6.26777*	3.063	0.042
		>50	4.782	3.370	0.157
41–50 years		Below 30 years	-14.78141*	5.799	0.011
		31–40 years	-6.26777*	3.063	0.042
		> 50 years	-1.486	3.418	0.664
> 50 years		<30 years	-13.29540*	5.967	0.027
		31–40 years	-4.782	3.370	0.157
		41–50 years	1.486	3.418	0.664

Hypothesis I

H0: There is no association in between use of technology in HR strategies and its effectiveness in recruitment process, managing talent and AI-driven tools used in the recruitment process

Table 7.3: Q1 and Q2 tabulation

Q1 and Q2 tabulation							
	Q2						Total
	1	2	3	4	5		
Q1	1	1	0	1	3	0	5
	% within Q1	20	0	20	60	0	
	% within Q2	50	0	3.85	2.8	0	2.87
	2	0	0	2	12	1	15
	% within Q1	0	0	13.34	80	6.67	
	% within Q2	0	0	7.69	11.21	2.77	8.62
	3	0	1	11	22	7	41
	% within Q1	0	2.44	26.83	53.66	17.07	
	% within Q2	0	33.34	42.3	20.56	19.45	23.56
	4	0	2	7	54	18	81
	% within Q1	0	2.46	8.64	66.67	22.23	
	% within Q2	0	66.67	26.92	50.46	50	46.55
	5	1	0	5	16	10	32
	% within Q1	3.12	0	15.62	50	31.25	
% within Q2	50	0	19.23	14.95	27.78	18.39	
Total	2	3	26	107	36	174	

H1: There is association in between use of technology in HR strategies and its effectiveness in recruitment process, managing talent and AI-driven tools used in the recruitment process

Q1: Your company's HR strategies using technology are effective in managing talent and ensuring employee satisfaction.

Q2: AI-driven tools and technologies are used effectively in the recruitment process in your organization.

There is a good association between higher values of **Q1** and **Q2**. The study indicates a positive correlation between HR strategies using technology and effectiveness of AI-driven recruitment tools. As employee satisfaction with HR strategies improves (higher Q1 values), respondents believe that AI-driven tools as effective (higher Q2 values).

Hypothesis II

H0: There is no association in between use of AI-enabled systems, such as chatbots or predictive analytics in recruitment and effectiveness in attracting skilled professionals

H1: There is association in between use of AI-enabled systems, such as chatbots or predictive analytics in recruitment and effectiveness in attracting skilled professionals

Q4: AI-enabled systems, such as chatbots or predictive analytics, are instrumental in improving candidate experience during the recruitment process.

Q5: The latest recruitment technologies adopted by your company are effective in attracting skilled IT professionals for onsite and offsite roles.

Table 7.4: Chi-Square Test

Statistic	Value
Chi-Square	20.96
Degrees of Freedom (df)	9
Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	0.0128

The **p-value 0.0128** < 0.05 which indicates significant relationship as the standard significance level is less than 0.05

The p-value shows the probability of observing value under the assumption that H0 is true.

Responses to **Q1** and **Q2** are **not independent**. This indicates that AI-enabled systems help in improving candidate experience. It is related to perceptions that effectiveness of recruitment technologies helps in attracting skilled IT professionals to the organisation.

Hypothesis III

H0: There is no association in between HR strategies using technology and on-site and off-site talent management deployed in ensuring high HR performances

H1: There is association in between HR strategies using technology and on-site and off-site talent management deployed in ensuring high HR performances

Q1: Your company's HR strategies using technology are effective in managing talent and ensuring employee satisfaction.

Q15: The HR strategies particularly for on-site and off-site talent management deployed by your company are effective in ensuring high HR performances.

Table 7.5: Chi -Square Test

Statistic	Value
Chi-Square	14.4261189
Degrees of Freedom	12
p-value	0.274328469

Since the **p-value** is greater than 0.05 **null hypothesis is rejected**.

Effectiveness of HR strategies using technology doesn't have significant influence on-site or off-site talent management. The lack of association shows that these two dimensions of HR strategies should be viewed separately by respondents.

Descriptive statistics and Spearman's correlation to start.

- **Mean & Standard Deviation** helps in understanding the central tendency and spread of responses
- Spearman's correlation works best with ordinal or non-normally distributed data
- **Frequency Distribution** shows how responses are spread across categories.

Since there is no significant influence test can be performed for **the strength and direction of monotonic relationships** between **HR strategies using technology, On-site talent management, Off-site talent management**.

Descriptive Statistics for Q1 and Q15

Table 7.6: Q1 and Q15

	Q1	Q15
count	195	195
mean	3.67	4.07
std	0.97	0.703
min	1	2
25%	3	4
50%	4	4
75%	4	5
max	5	5

Spearman Correlation Results

Table 7.7: Spearman Correlation

Metric	Value
Spearman Correlation	0.037
p-value	0.607

Spearman's Rank Correlation:

Correlation Coefficient: 0.037 (very weak positive relationship).

p-value: 0.6076 > 0.05

There is no significant correlation between Q1 and Q15, which indicates that there is no significant relationship with two variables.

Hypothesis IV

H0: There is no association with HR strategies using technology in effectively managing talent and Innovative mobile applications used in recruitment

H1: There is an association with HR strategies using technology in effectively managing talent and Innovative mobile applications used in recruitment

Table 7.8: Chi-Square

Aspect	Value
Chi-Square Statistic	14.43
Degrees of Freedom (df)	12
p-value	0.2743
Significance Level (α)	0.05

Analysis shows no significant association between Q1 and Q18. The effectiveness of HR strategies using technology doesn't indicate use of mobile applications in IT mass recruitment and hence appear to be **independent**.

Hypothesis V

H0: There is no association between HR strategies using technology in effectively managing talent and ensuring employee satisfaction and overall organizational performance.

H1: There is an association between HR strategies using technology in effectively managing talent and ensuring employee satisfaction and overall organizational performance.

Q1: Your company's HR strategies using technology are effective in managing talent and ensuring employee satisfaction.

Q20: IT recruitment and talent acquisition in your company are effective in the overall organizational performance.

Table 7.9: Chi-Square

Aspect	Value
Chi-Square Statistic	25.67
Degrees of Freedom	12
p-value	0.013

Since $p=0.013 < 0.05$. This shows a significant relation between HR strategies using technology and IT recruitment effectiveness. The result shows that HR strategies are supported with the help of technology it reflects in effectiveness IT recruitment and organizational performance.

Table 7.10: Normality table

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z</i>	<i>P value</i>
Employee Engagement and Satisfaction	163	26.63	5.02	1.036	0.151
Technology and AI in Talent Acquisition	163	31.42	5.38	1.067	0.144
Innovation in Recruitment Practices	163	30.72	5.38	1.426	0.078
Technology-Driven Recruitment	163	32.69	5.94	1.122	0.131

The K-S test was conducted, and the following table gives the results of the K-S test. The test indicates that the data is standard.

RELIABILITY

Table 7.11: RELIABILITY

Path	Regression coefficients	Critical Ratio (CR)	P	Variance explained (%)
TTA → EES	0.721	25.479	<0.001	84.8
IRP → EES	0.858	30.676	<0.001	91.8
TDR → EES	0.796	4.873	<0.001	88.8

Table 7.11 shows Cronbach’s Alpha value is > 0.7 so the requirement condition is satisfied and ensures the reliability of questionnaire.

CFA test conducted in the observed set of data shows that the overall correlated CFA model shows a good reasonable fit ($\chi^2 = 96.154$, CFI = 0.966, GFI = 0.939, RMR = 0.013, RMSEA = 0.063, TLI = 0.928). It confirms that there is reasonable fit for this measurement model. Scale used to measure be valid and reliable. Thus, the study can be used to proceed for hypothesis testing.

Table 7.12: RELIABILITY

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
Employee Engagement and Satisfaction	0.932	5
Technology and AI in Talent Acquisition	0.935	5
Innovation in Recruitment Practices	0.938	4
Technology-Driven Recruitment	0.867	4

The result exhibited in table 7.12 that the innovation in Recruitment Practices has more (.858) towards the Employee Engagement and Satisfaction. The next influence in to the Employee Engagement and Satisfaction was created by the Technology-Driven Recruitment (.796). The least influence towards the Employee Engagement and Satisfaction Technology and AI in Talent Acquisition (.721)

Regression equation is $EES = .858IRP + .796TDR + .721TTA$

Expected contributions and conclusion

Findings

This study has come to an understanding that technology has a significant impact on making the organisation effective. TCS, Wipro, and CTS, three leading IT firms in Cochin, were taken to understand the impact of technology on employee engagement and satisfaction. Impact of technology on the process of recruitment was studied. The study used a questionnaire to analyse technology and AI's impact on talent acquisition. A questionnaire with Likert scale statements was used to collect data. It was ensured to check the reliability and consistency of the survey which was done with statistical validation.

AI Adoption and Employee Engagement: A significant correlation is shown between technology and employee engagement. Integrating AI-driven tools has contributed a lot to making the recruitment process reliable. When recruitment process in an organisation is highly streamlined and effective it is seen that it led to higher levels of employee engagement.

Technology and Employee Satisfaction: Many advanced methods for recruitment using technology have helped in improving employee satisfaction. Streamlining the recruitment processes has a significant influence in changing candidate perceptions about the organisation and improving job satisfaction.

AI-Enabled Onboarding Systems: Onboarding systems in many organisations involves stepwise process. When technology is used for automating the process and providing significant order for the activities involved it in turn makes the experience of employees seamless. The analysis showed a good association between AI-enabled and improved employee engagement.

Time-to-Hire Efficiency: The study found bottlenecks in the hiring process. There is a significant link between technology utilization in recruitment and time required to complete and onboard a candidate in the organisation.

Social Media Recruitment: Every recruitment process becomes effective when it can reach broader and diverse talent pool. The findings revealed that being effective in social media platforms helps in spreading the news about openings in the organisation to larger set of potential candidates. The innovative recruitment practices also help in attaining attention of more talent pool.

These findings underscore technological advancements are interconnected to employee engagement and satisfaction. Most of the advanced technologies and AI tools helps in incorporating innovative practices in the organisation. Need for IT firms to align their recruitment strategies along with technology helps in attracting and retaining top talent effectively.

Suggestions

Integration of AI and Advanced Technologies: Predictive analytics is a feature of AI where lot of forecasting can be done using data this can help in understanding the profile of numerous candidates who have applied for an opening in the organisation. Chatbots and automated applicant tracking systems can be used to make the communication more effective and easier. Organizations have to use such AI-driven tools. These tools will help the organisation in enhancing the recruitment experience for candidates.

Innovative Recruitment Strategies: Improving engagement is the main purpose of recruitment process. This innovation can be made with implementation of technology. Various methods like gamified assessments where employees are made to involve in process through various tasks, virtual reality-based interviews where technology is used to replicate a real-life scenario in front of the candidate. Digital platforms used in IT firms help them in identifying more candidates and attract them to recruitment practices.

Leverage social media for Recruitment: Social media recruitment strategy helps in attracting larger talent pools. Firms should use platforms like LinkedIn and Instagram to project their organisation values and work culture. It can be also used to advertise job openings and interact with potential candidates to have an initial background analysis.

Enhanced Onboarding Processes: Onboarding systems helps in automating administrative tasks in an organisation. AI-enabled technology provides seamless and engaging experience for the employees like offering personalized onboarding paths, and leveraging virtual assistants for real-time support.

Continuous Training for HR Professionals: Leveraging new tools effectively for regular training and upskilling programs can be made easy with technology. HR professionals should be updated about emerging recruitment technologies and best practices in the organisation.

Regular Feedback Mechanisms: Improving overall satisfaction of employees can be only achieved through maintain a regular mechanism to gather feedback. Organizations should use data from candidates and employees about their experience during the recruitment process and issues they experienced during onboarding. Thus, when technology is implemented to collect this information, it can used effectively by the organisation.

IT firms can improve talent acquisition practices by aligning their HR strategies with technology. An organisation which practices these modern strategies where technology has a prominent role result in providing a good environment in the organisation. These systems foster a more engaging and satisfying recruitment experience for candidates and employees. These strategies provide a competitive edge in attracting and retaining top talent in the dynamic IT sector.

Conclusion

The study is conducted to understand the impact of technology and AI on talent acquisition and their influence on employee engagement and satisfaction within leading IT firms in Cochin (TCS, Wipro, and CTS). The study came to an understanding that there is a significant role of technologies in talent acquisition. Various innovative strategies in recruitment process can be obtained by adopting advanced technology.

The survey was done by a questionnaire which was statically validated. High internal consistency was observed in the questionnaire which ensures data accuracy. Chi-Square tests showed the prominent role of technology and AI in enhancing recruitment efficiency. The Significant correlations was identified between technology use and engagement.

The study emphasized leveraging AI can have a pivotal role in managing an IT organisation. Innovative techniques that are done in IT organisation helps improving organisational effectiveness which is achieved by maintaining the employees who are right fit the organisation. Practical implications of technologies like predictive analytics and other technologies have optimized talent acquisition processes. Use of social media platforms have helped in reaching a larger talent pool which can contain a lot of prospective candidates. Aligning recruitment strategies with technology advancements help the organization in improving candidate experiences. Which in turn results enhancement of engagement of employee with organisation and result in long-term employee retention and organizational success.

IT sector is subject to rapid technological evolution, the insights from this study provide a framework for integrating technology and innovation into HR practices. By adopting the recommendations outlined, organizations can strengthen their competitive positioning, attract top-tier talent, and sustain growth in the fast-paced IT industry. This research serves as a foundation for future studies exploring the transformative potential of AI and technology in talent acquisition and employee satisfaction.

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